

References

- Z. MACHON, D. UGOSZ and M. MORDARSKI, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1980, 93, 709; S. OZAKI, Y. WATANABE, T. HOSHIKO, H. MIZUNO, K. ISHIKAWA and H. MORI, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1984, 101, 55035; T. UEDA, J. SAKAKIBARA and J. NAKAGAMI, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1984, 101, 38418; J. HUNG and L. WARBEL, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1984, 21, 741; A. KREUTZBERGER and J. GILLESSEN, *Arch. Chem.*, 1984, 317, 749 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1984, 101, 211094); J. C. GAGE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 469; H. ECK, F. MUELLER and S. WIHRHEIM, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1974, 81, 120676; K. M. GHONEIM, F. EL-TELBANY and K. YOUSSEF, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, 63, 714
- W. J. HALE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 36, 104.
- H. L. GAGGAD, K. N. WADODKAR and B. J. GHIYA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1985, 24, 1244; V. J. NAPHADE and B. J. GHIYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, 63, 851.

Synthesis and Antibacterial Activity of Nitrofurfuraldehyde as-Triazino[5,6-*b*]indol-3-ylhydrazones

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A number of as-triazino[5,6-*b*]indoles are reported to possess antiviral, analgesic and hypertensive properties¹⁻⁴. Prompted by the pharmacological importance of triazinoindoles and as a part of our

general search for pharmacologically active nitrofuran compounds^{5,6}, we report herein the synthesis and biological activities of some substituted-nitrofurfuraldehyde as-triazino-indolyl hydrazones.

The reaction of substituted-isatins and thio-semicarbazide provides a convenient method for the synthesis of 3-mercapto-as-triazino[5,6-*b*]indoles⁷. These mercapto compounds on hydrazinolysis yielded as-triazino[5,6-*b*]indol-3-ylhydrazines (1) which are characterised by elemental analysis. These indolylhydrazines when condensed with nitrofurfural diacetate in alcohol medium using concentrated sulphuric acid as catalyst yielded the required nitrofurfuraldehyde hydrazones (2). The structures of these compounds are confirmed by elemental analysis, ir and mass spectral data (Table 1).

All the new compounds were analysed satisfactorily for C, H and N. Fairly intense to weak molecular ion peaks were observed in the mass spectra of these hydrazones. In all cases fragment peaks were also observed corresponding to ions obtained by the loss of NO₂ and CO from the molecular ions.

Antibacterial activities of nitrofurfuraldehyde hydrazones (2a-j) determined against *S. aureus*, *A. aerogenes*, *E. coli* and *B. subtilis* by disc-diffusion method, revealed that 2c possessing dichloro substitution at the benzene ring has antibacterial activity comparable to that of furacin. The antibacterial activities of the compounds diminished when the indole NH was alkylated by methyl and ethyl substituents

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2a-j

Compd. R	R ¹	Yield %	M.p. °C	Molecular formula*	ν_{max} (nujol; cm ⁻¹)		M ⁺	m/z (% abundance)	
					NO ₂	NH		M-NO ₂	M-NO ₂ -CO
2a	H	H	>360	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₇ O ₂	1 380, 1 540	Too weak	323 (49.5)	277 (100)	249 (61.2)
2b	H	8-Chloro	215-17	C ₁₄ H ₈ ClN ₇ O ₂	1 380, 1 540	3 600m	357/359 (20.5)	311 (26.8)	283 (25.6)
2c	H	6,8-Dichloro	284-85	C ₁₄ H ₇ Cl ₂ N ₇ O ₂	1 380, 1 540	3 650w			
2d	H	8-Methyl	304-05	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₇ O ₂	1 380, 1 520	3 550w	337 (18.4)	291 (26.3)	263 (21.3)
2e	Methyl	H	295-96	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₇ O ₂	1 375, 1 520	Too weak	337 (90.2)	291 (100)	263 (51.0)
2f	Ethyl	H	264-66	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₇ O ₂	1 380, 1 540	Too weak			
2g	Methyl	8-Chloro	316-18	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ ClN ₇ O ₂	1 380, 1 540	3 600m			
2h	Ethyl	8-Chloro	322-25	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ ClN ₇ O ₂	1 380, 1 540	3 600m			
2i	Methyl	8-Methyl	270-72	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₇ O ₂	1 380, 1 540	3 600m	351 (24.8)	305 (100)	277 (46.3)
2j	Methyl	6-8-Dichloro	307-08	C ₁₅ H ₉ Cl ₂ N ₇ O ₂	1 375, 1 540	3 500w			

*Satisfactory C, H and N analyses were obtained.

Experimental

All the melting points were determined by capillary method and are uncorrected. The mass spectra of some compounds were recorded on a Jeol JMS-D 300 spectrometer. 3-Mercapto-as-triazino[5,6-*b*]indoles were obtained according to literature methods².

as-Triazino[5,6-*b*]indol-3-ylhydrazines (1): The corresponding 3-mercapto-*as*-triazino[5,6-*b*]indole (0.01 mol) was refluxed with hydrazine hydrate (10 ml; 98%) with occasional shaking for 1–1.5 h. The resulting solid product was washed with alcohol and dried. The product was recrystallised from aqueous DMF to yield fine pale yellow crystals of 1.

Scheme 1

Similarly, the other hydrazines are prepared: R=H, R'=6,8-dichloro, 80%, m.p. 305–06°; R=H, R'=8-methyl, 75%, m.p. 286–87°; R=methyl, R'=8-chloro, 65%, m.p. 325°; R=ethyl, R'=8-chloro, 65%, m.p. 334–35°; R=methyl, R'=8-methyl, 65%, m.p. 265–66°; R=methyl, R'=6,8-dichloro, 70%, m.p. 258°.

*Nitrofurfuraldehyde as-triazino[5,6-*b*]indol-3-ylhydrazine (2a)*: To a solution of 1a (1.0 g, 0.005 mol) in alcohol (50 ml), nitrofurfural diacetate (1.2 g, 0.005 mol) and concentrated H₂SO₄ (0.5 ml) were added and the contents refluxed for 3 h. The reaction mixture on removal of alcohol, yielded the corresponding hydrazone. The resulting solid was filtered and recrystallised from aqueous DMF to yield the title compound (2a).

Similarly, 2b–j were prepared (Table 1).

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References

- Allen and Hanburys Ltd. Neth. Pat. 6 410 8238/1965 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1965, 63, 13295).
- J. M. Z. GLADYCH, R. HORBY, J. H. HUNT, D. JACK, J. J. BOYLE, F. J. FERLAUTO, R. F. HAFF, C. G. KORMENDY, F. J. STAMFIELD and R. C. STEWART, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1972, 15, 277.
- A. B. TOMCHIN, M. A. IGNAT'eva and G. F. MASYUTA, *Khim. Farm. Z. L.*, 1972, 6, 23.
- D. KAMINSKY US Pat. 3 752 891/1973 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1973, 79, 1493286).
- B. S. HOLLA, B. KALLURAYA and K. R. SRIDHAR, *Curr. Sci.*, 1987, 56, 585.
- B. S. HOLLA and K. V. UDUPA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1988, 57, 79.

Chemical Constituents of *Spilanthes paniculata*

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IN continuation of our studies on an annual herb of Tripura, *Spilanthes paniculata* Wall. ex DC^{1,2} (Fam: *Compositae*), we now report the isolation and characterisation of stearic acid, tetratriacontanoic acid, sitosterol, stigmasterol and sitosterol-*O*-β-D-glucoside from the aerial parts of the plant.

Aerial parts of the plant collected from Khayerpur (Agartala), were air-dried, milled and extracted (1.0 kg) with petrol (b.p. 60–80°) and 90% ethanol successively in a soxhlet. The petrol extract was concentrated to a residue (6.5 g) and column chromatographed through Si-gel. The residue from the benzene eluate on recolumn chromatography afforded two crystalline compounds, A (0.06 g) and B (0.015 g). The compound A, m.p. 68° (*M*⁺ 284), was identified as stearic acid by its colour reaction with starch-iodide paper, positive bicarbonate test and spectral (ir, ¹H nmr and mass) studies and finally by co-glc of its Me-ester with an authentic Me-sterate in a 10% PEGA column. Compound B, C₃₄H₆₈O₂ (*M*⁺ 508), m.p. 93° gave positive starch-iodide and bicarbonate tests for carboxylic acids; ν_{max} (KBr) 2 920, 2 850, 1 709 (C=O) and 1 460 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃, 100 MHz) 0.88 (3H, t, Me), 1.24 (62H, br s, 31 CH₂) and 2.32 (2H, t, CH₂ adjacent to C=O); *m/z* (rel. intensity%) 508 [*M*⁺ (12.5), 480 [*M*-28]⁺ (60.0), 452 [*M*-2×28]⁺ (62.5), 424 (40.0), 396 (25.0), 368 (18.0), 340 (7.5), 312 (15.0), 284 (25.0), 256 (37.5), 228 (17.5), 200 (12.5),